

Study of frequency: Viable and Chlorophyll mutation in chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.)

Vinay Panwar¹

Swami Viveka Nand Subharti University, Meerut, Monad University, Hapur (U.P), India
Email: swamivinaypanwar@gmail.com

Partap Singh

Swami Viveka Nand Subharti University, Meerut, Monad University, Hapur (U.P), India

V. K. Dwivedi

Janta Vedic (PG), College, Baraut Baghpat (U.P), India

Abstract: The chlorophyll mutation frequency in the M_2 generation is the most effective and dependable index for evaluating the genetic effects of mutagenic treatments. In general, all mutagenic treatments induced a fairly high frequency of chlorophyll mutations. It is also obvious from these results that chlorophyll mutation rate increased with an increasing dose of radiation (gamma-rays) exception in few cases, whereas a medium dose of chemicals was found to be the most efficient for inducing chlorophyll mutations. The present investigation is found to have obtained a higher frequency of chlorophyll mutation with medium or low doses mutagens. It seems that the strong mutagens reach their saturation point even at lower doses in the highly mutable genotypes, and a further increase in dose does not add to mutation frequency, with an increase in dose beyond a point, the strong mutagens become more toxic than the higher dose of relatively weaker mutagens. It was assumed that specific chemical reactions would take place between a mutagen and gene mutations in a definite manner if the right chemical applied. Several morphological characters through different mutagens i.e. xantha > albino > viridis, are founded respectively.

Keywords: Chickpea, spectrum, frequency and chlorophyll

Introduction:

The mutation has been a dominant tool to produce new additional heritable variation which may be utilized in traditional recombination breeding program Mutation breeding program needs to be sufficiently standardized for improvement of polygenic traits to gain general confidence and wide acceptance of its use among the breeders so that experiments could be planned with reasonable expectations of success. The induced mutation in fundamental studies, induced mutagenesis can be used to create additional variability for quantitative traits. The success of a mutation breeding program depends not only on the quality of induced mutation but also on the screening techniques to identify these mutations, which occur with a very low frequency among a large number of others of little breeding value. An attempt has been made here to develop standard screening techniques for micro mutations affecting the polygenic system. In general, selection for quantitative traits, such as yield, should be preferably carried out in early generations because most

¹ Corresponding author

of the desired combinations of favorable alleles are likely to be lost in advanced generations due to intensive or even no selection for other traits. It became a common practice to advance only normal-looking M_3 plants to M_2 generation and apply the first cycle of selection not earlier than M_3 . This results in an increased volume of non-mutated material and delays in the isolation of promising variants. This was most probably because the material already selected once in M_2 was confirmed with higher probability in subsequent generations. Even if the material selected in M_2 generations has a higher probability of getting fixed as promising strains, there is no evidence to suggest that the frequency of promising mutations per se over the entire population is higher in M_2 than M_3 . Therefore, an attempt has been made to explore the possibility of selecting for polygenic variability in an early generation (M_2) following treatments with three mutagens.

Materials and Methods:

The experimental materials for this study consisted of 3 varieties of chickpea having a good agronomic base and belonging to diverse group viz., V_1 Desi (BGM-524), V_2 Kabuli (BG-1053) and V_3 green seeded (KSB-220) were treated with different doses of gamma rays ethyl methane sulphonate (EMS) and their combination (EMS + Gamma rays, details are presented in below:

Mutagens:

The physical-chemical and combined mutagens were employed to induce mutations. The brief description of the source mode of action and method of application is given below:

Table 1 Details of mutagens and their doses for each three varieties used in present investigation

Mutagen	Dose	No. of seeds treated	Treatment condition
Control	0.00	100×3	Dry
Gamma rays	20kR	100×3	Dry
	30kR	100×3	Dry
	40kR	100×3	Dry
	50kR	100×3	Dry
	60kR	100×3	Dry
	EMS	010%	100×3
015%		100×3	
020%		100×3	
025%		100×3	
030%		100×3	
Combined treatment	20kR+0.10	100×3	Dry + Soaking (400ml)
	30kR+0.15	100×3	
	40kR+0.15	100×3	
	50kR+0.15	100×3	
	60kR+0.15	100×3	

Total treatment = $16 \times 3 = 48$

Total experimental seeds = $48 \times 100 = 4800$

Physical mutagen:

The gamma rays obtained from a 2000 curie CO^{60} gamma cell installed in the Division of NRL, IARI New Delhi with a dose rate of 2500 rads per minute was used as a physical mutagen. Gamma rays are an electromagnetic type of radiations induce mutations through ionization when a biological material is irradiated a gamma rays photon hits an orbital electron of the atom. The electron gets excited and in turn ejected tremendous energy and is capable of causing further ionization along its path. Well-dried uniform seeds of each variety size about 10 percent moisture content were filled in a seed envelope and exposed to gamma rays irradiations in the gamma cell. Different doses of gamma rays were used for irradiation of seeds i.e. 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, and 60 kR accordingly. Chemical mutagen Ethyl methane sulphonate (EMS) a potent alkylating agent obtained from Eastman Kodak Chemicals USA was used as a chemical mutagen. It is the most widely used chemical mutagen and is also a powerful carcinogen. It induces through alkylation of DNA.

Well dried selected seeds of uniform size were presoaked in water for 6 hours and then treated with freshly prepared aqueous solutions of EMS at $25 \pm 2^{\circ}C$. To have maximum absorption of the solution, the seeds contained in the conical flask were repeatedly subjected to shaking. Treatments with five different concentrations i.e. 0.10, 0.15, 0.20, 0.25 and 0.30 percent for 4 to 6 hr each were given with intermittent shaking. As soon as treatment is over, seeds were washed in running tap water for 5-10 minutes to remove traces of chemicals from the seed surface. Thereafter by spreading the seeds on blotting paper excessive water was removed. The seeds were sown in the field immediately after treatment whereas seeds soaked in tap water for 6 hours were used as control. Combined mutagen. Seeds irradiated at different doses viz. 20, 30, 40, 50, and 60 kR were treated with 0.10, 0.15, 0.20, 0.25, and 0.30 percent EMS aqueous solution of ethyl methane sulphonate for 6 hr by the method described above.

The investigation was carried out from research farm at Monad University and Janta Vaidic College Baraut Baghpat U.P on M_1 and M_2 generations. Both generations were grown in well-prepared land and data taken very precautionary. The experimental material in M_1 and M_2 generations was handled as described below:

M_1 Generations:

The M_1 generation was raised with control and treated seeds at a distance of 45 cm between rows and 25 cm between seeds within a row. The recommended agronomic, cultivar, and plant protection practices were followed to raise a good crop. The characters were recorded M_1 generation in during the entire crop season.

M_2 Generations:

The individual M_1 plant progenies were sown in the field in separate M_2 progeny and data were recorded following characters.

Chlorophyll Mutation:

All the treated, as well as control progenies, were screened for the frequency and spectrum of chlorophyll mutations from emergence until the age of 4 weeks after sowing. Mutation frequency was estimated on a population basis as well as the percentage of segregating M_1 plant

progenies in each treatment. The spectrum by chlorophyll mutation was studied and the mutants were classified as per the scheme of Lamprecht (Blixt, 1972) with modification.

Using the data obtained on chlorophyll mutations both mutagenic effectiveness is a measure of the frequency of mutation induced by a unit dose on mutagen, while mutagenic efficiency gives an idea of the proportion of the mutations in relation to the total biological damage measured through lethality and sterility etc. The mutagenic effectiveness and efficiency were determined as per the formulae suggested by Konzak et.al (1965) as follows.

$$\text{Mutagenic effectiveness} = \frac{\text{Mutation rate (\%M}_2 \text{ seedlings)}}{(\text{Gamma rays}) \quad \text{Dose in Gy}}$$

$$\text{Mutagenic effectiveness} = \frac{\text{Mutation rate (\%M}_2 \text{ seedlings)}}{(\text{Chemical treatment}) \quad \text{concentration x time}}$$

$$\text{Mutagenic efficiency} = \frac{\text{Mutation rate (\%M}_2 \text{ seedlings)}}{\% \text{ lethality or sterility}}$$

Throughout the entire growth, period all M₂ progenies were examined several times to detect viable mutations affecting various morphological attributes. The frequency of morphological mutations was also calculated as earlier for the chlorophyll mutations.

Mutation frequency:

The frequencies of chlorophyll and morphological mutations were estimated as follows:

M₂ family basis (percentage of segregating M₂ progenies)

$$\text{Mutation frequency (\%)} = \frac{\text{No. of mutated progenies} \times 100}{\text{Total M}_2 \text{ progenies}}$$

M₂ Population basis (percentage of mutated M₂ plants or mutants)

$$\text{Mutation frequency (\%)} = \frac{\text{No. of Mutants} \times 100}{\text{Total M}_2 \text{ progenies}}$$

Results and Discussion:

The frequency of chlorophyll mutation recorded on the basis of M₁ plant (M₂ progenies) with some suitable modifications are shown following. The chlorophyll mutations were identified in M₂ generation in Table 2 given below.

1. Spectrum and frequency of chlorophyll and viable mutations
2. Estimates of the totals mutations rate

Albina: The color of young seedlings was white on germination and they did not survive after a week from germination. No chlorophyll or carotenoids was found absent.

Xantha: The color of young seedling was yellow, high pale yellow or orange but they did not survive beyond two weeks. The carotenoids were present but chlorophyll was absent.

Chlorina: The color seedling was greenish-yellow/yellowish-green and started dying within 10-15 days after germination, few survived a little longer without seed setting.

Viridis: Light green, fully viable and more or less normally productive.

Chlorophyll mutation: The variety BGM-524 of chickpea was noticeably different in chlorophyll mutation under different treatments showed in table 1. chlorophyll mutation based on different seedlings were classified on the lines suggested by Gustafson (1940). Mutation rates under various treatments have been represented the under following heads:

Chlorophyll mutation frequency:

Table 2 shows that highest (1.40%) frequency of chlorophyll mutation was observed under (0.30%) EMS followed by (1.20%) under 20 Kr + 0.10% EMS treatments while the lowest (0.20%) being under 0.15% EMS.

Frequency of viable mutation:

The spectrum and frequency of induced chlorophyll viable mutations are presented in Table 2. The maximum leaf morphological mutation was shown in 0.15% EMS (2.00%) and lowest (0.20%) in 50 kR treatments of gamma rays. The maximum (0.80%) plant type mutation were shown in 30 kR + 0.15% EMS treatments and the lowest (0.20%) under 30 kR dose of gamma-rays and 0.20% EMS. The maximum (0.80%) frequency was observed under 20 kR + 0.10% EMS and the lowest (0.20%) under 30 kR, 60 kR of gamma rays and 0.10% and 0.20% EMS dose for pod type mutation. The highest 0.60% frequency and percentage of seed type mutation was observed under 0.15% EMS and 50 kR +0.25%, while the lowest 0.20% was observed under 20 kR dose of gamma rays, 0.20% EMS, 20 kR +0.10% EMS and 40 kR + 0.20% EMS.

Table -2 Spectrum and frequency of induced chlorophyll mutation for BGM-524 in M2 generation

Treatments	No of M2	Types of mutations								Total mutant in M2	
		Chlorina		Xantha		Albina		Viridis		Plant (overall)	
		No	%	No	%	No	%	No.	%	No	%
Control	500	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
20 kR	500	-	-	-	-	2	0.40	-	-	2	0.40
30 kR	500	1	0.20	1	0.20	-	-	2	0.40	4	0.80
40 kR	500	2	0.40	-	0.40	1	0.20	-	-	3	0.60
50 kR	500	1	0.20	2	0.20	-	-	2	0.40	5	0.10
60 kR	500	1	0.20	1	-	2	0.40	-	-	4	0.80
0.10% EMS	500	1	0.20	-	-	3	0.60	2	0.40	6	0.12
0.15% EMS	500	-	-	-	-	1	0.20	-	-	1	0.20
0.20% EMS	500	2	0.40	-	-	-	-	1	0.20	3	0.60
0.25% EMS	500	1	0.20	-	0.40	1	0.20	2	0.40	4	0.80
0.30% EMS	500	-	-	2	0.80	1	0.20	4	0.80	7	1.40
20 kR+0.10% EMS	500	1	0.20	4	0.40	1	0.20	-	-	6	1.20
30 kR+0.15% EMS	500	-	-	2	0.20	-	-	1	0.20	3	0.60
40 kR+0.20% EMS	500	1	0.20	1	-	-	-	-	-	2	0.40
50 kR+0.25% EMS	500	2	0.40	-	-	2	0.40	-	-	4	0.80
60 kR+0.30% EMS	500	1	0.20	-	-	1	0.20	2	0.40	5	1.00
Total	500	14		13		15		17		59	-

Table 3. Range population mean, CV, heritability and genetic advance for days to 50% flowering in M₂ generation for V₁V₂ and V₃

Statistical	Parameter	UGamma rays (kR)U					UEthylmethancesulphonate (EMS,%)U					UCombination (Gama rays kR+EMS,%)U						
		Control	20	30	40	50	60	1.10	0.15	0.20	0.25	0.30	20+0.10	30+0.15	40+0.20	50+0.25	60+0.30	
Range	V ₁	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10
		19.0	21.3	29.0	27.5	56.6	27.7	27.9	24.4	27.7	19.1	27.3	27.7	27.0	21.7	30.0	21.3	
	V ₂	16.0	11.0	11.0	11.0	6.3	11.1	11.0	11.2	11.1	7.4	17.3	11.1	11.3	8.7	6.8	11.3	
		26.0	31.0	37.0	39.5	27.2	40.3	31.0	29.3	27.7	33.3	32.4	33.1	19.3	19.3	29.3	29.9	
	V ₃	11.0	7.0	7.4	11.0	3.4	7.0	9.3	6.3	8.9	6.4	1.0	1.5	7.5	11.4	4.4	7.1	
		19.7	21.3	27.0	22.8	29.3	17.5	36.3	19.5	27.9	27.7	10.3	27.7	27.0	30.0	22.4	21.2	
Mean	V ₁	13.39	13.16	14.66	14.48	14.13	18.34	15.80	17.63	17.57	9.87	14.30	15.92	15.70	13.64	18.42	15.81	
	V ₂	21.00	18.38	23.23	25.82	14.33	25.30	23.03	21.50	19.31	17.46	24.57	19.93	24.06	13.84	18.66	22.71	
	V ₃	14.20	13.26	14.11	14.47	13.57	12.50	18.21	19.91	18.60	16.39	5.55	14.31	14.88	17.44	14.15	14.05	
	CV	17.64	21.73	30.01	40.74	56.05	29.60	32.59	28.07	41.52	53.59	49.03	43.34	28.47	21.48	31.48	22.13	
Heritability	V ₁	17.64	21.73	30.01	40.74	56.05	29.60	32.59	28.07	41.52	53.59	49.03	43.34	28.47	21.48	31.48	22.13	
	V ₂	24.14	29.43	26.90	24.40	36.15	24.74	25.23	23.67	27.19	30.18	14.57	27.25	21.03	16.44	36.55	23.21	
	V ₃	19.15	23.22	25.42	19.58	45.48	20.80	48.88	24.17	29.73	30.50	45.05	46.12	28.96	30.10	30.17	22.92	
Genetic advance	V ₁	17.64	21.73	30.01	40.74	56.05	29.60	32.59	28.07	41.52	53.59	49.03	43.34	28.47	21.48	31.48	22.13	
	V ₂	24.14	29.43	26.90	24.40	36.15	24.74	25.23	23.67	27.19	30.18	14.57	27.25	21.03	16.44	36.55	23.21	
	V ₃	19.15	23.22	25.42	19.58	45.48	20.80	48.88	24.17	29.73	30.50	45.05	46.12	28.96	30.10	30.17	22.92	
V ₁ = BGM-524 (desi) V ₂ =BG-1053 kabuli V ₃ =KSB-220(green)																		

Figure: Stages of Experiment (Source: authors)

Total mutation rate:

The total (chlorophyll + viable) mutation under various treatments are presented in Table 2. The mutation rate most of the treatments are deviated between (1.4 - 3.0%) except for the treatments 40 kR (1.20%) having 4 plants. The total mutation rate in treatments of gamma rays was observed less comparison in comparison to the treatments of EMS with a different concentration on the basis of Table 2, it is clear from the combined treatments of gamma rays with ethyl methane sulphonate had more mutation rate in BGM-524 genotypes.

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